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Research Article

NEEDLE STICK INJURIES: AWARENESS AND PRACTICES OF PRECAUTIONARY MEASURES AMONG HEALTH CARE WORKERS OF PUBLIC AND PRIVATE HOSPITALS IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract:

Introduction: Needle stick injuries (NSIs) is the most frequently occurring accidental injuries in the health care settings resulting from the penetration of contaminated syringes or sharps that may expose health care workers (HCWs) to serious life threatening illnesses. NSIs are amongst the most common occupational hazards and potential source of transmission of to more than 20 fatal blood borne infections including Hepatitis B&C and HIV etc.

Objectives: To ascertain the awareness of HCWs regarding needle stick injuries in public and private sector hospitals as well as to compare this awareness in both public and private sector healthcare facilities.

Material and Methods: The study was a cross sectional survey conducted in public and private sector hospitals in Hyderabad, Pakistan from October 2018 to March 2019. HCWs include; nursing staff, midwives, Operation Theater and Intensive care unit technicians were invited. Data was collected using written questionnaire designed specifically for this study. Questions related to the participant's knowledge of NSIs and its precautionary measures as well as their routine practices during their routine duties were included.

Results: Two hundred HCWs participated in this study. Most (53%) of them were from private sector hospital while majority (36%) of them belongs to age group 28 to 37 years. Half of them (53%) were aware of NSIs while almost two third of them knew about the diseases spread by NSIs. Moreover, 53% of them were aware of the precautionary measures of NSIs. Majority (27%) of HCWs from public hospitals believe that during medication, most of NSIs occur in comparison with private hospital participants where majority (23%) thinks that breaking and discarding needles with bare hands most frequently cause NSIs. Majority (53%) of them not use tray to keep syringes while majority (58%) do not use needle cutter for disposing used needles. There was a statistically significant difference p value < 0.05 in awareness level of HCWs in public and private sector hospitals.

Conclusion: Prevalence of NSI was high among the nursing staff in both health sectors. Low awareness level was demonstrated among the HCWs of public sector hospital. There was a significant difference in awareness related to knowledge and precautionary measures of NSIs between public and private sector hospitals.

Keywords: NSIs, HCWs, Awareness, Hepatitis B and C

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INTRODUCTION:

Needle stick injury (NSI) defined are the injuries or wounds caused as result of accidental penetration of skin by needles or sharps [1]. These are the commonest of all risk factors of accidental injuries that may occur anytime when people use, discard and dispose the syringes or sharps in hospital settings [2]. Such injuries are amongst the most common occupational hazards that may expose the health care workers (HCWs) to more than 20 fatal blood borne infections such as hepatitis B, hepatitis C and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) [3]. Such conditions resulting from occupational blood-exposure through injuries with sharp instruments and syringes [4]. Majority of the HCWs contract the diseases in health care settings without being aware of them [4].

Sometimes if used needles improperly disposed or left unattended, they may conceal with patient's bed linen or garbage and accidentally injure the HCWs or even common person. Globally around two million HCWs experienced NSIs every year [5].

Globally more than two third case of Hepatitis B & C and about 5% of HIV cases resulting from NSIs [5].

These injuries can also lead to serious psychological stress even in the absence of fatal infections. Such factor may pose more burden on health cost of person and resulting in loss of working time. Up to 12% of NSI cases may also leads to the psychiatric morbidity like post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) [6].

World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that every year around 16 billion injections given in developing and transitional countries to patients. Out of these, 90-95% injections used for therapeutic purpose or management of diseases while remaining 5-10% used for immunization and other purposes. While the global burden of diseases resulting from the occupational exposure to be 2.5% of the HIV infection and more than 40% of hepatitis B and C infections

among the HCWs. In United Kingdom (UK) alone, around 3773 NSIs reported between 1997 and 2007 to high-risk body fluids. [7]

Moreover, data from the two German hospitals indicate that about 500,000 NSIs occur every year in Germany. [3]

While, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) estimates that approximately 385,000 injuries related to needles and sharps annually to HCWs in the United States alone⁸. To prevent such injuries among the HCWs, WHO recommends following the precautionary measures and recommends the governments to use the safety injecting devices exclusively by the year 2020. Developed countries like Canada, USA, Brazil, UK and European Union (EU) countries have already endorsed legislation for the use of safety injection devices [9]. Despite an increased awareness and legislation in some countries, NSIs and their serious consequences still occur [10].

Pakistan comes in Eastern Mediterranean Region (EMRO), which unfortunately, has the highest rate of NSIs in comparison to the rest of the world [11]. Due to lack of awareness and proper legislation as well as overcrowding of the health facilities, NSIs are very common in hospitals of Pakistan [12]. Increased incidence of needle stick injuries in HCW is known to arise from a combination of high risk activities with low safety measures (activities including administering injections, drawing blood, recapping needles, disposing of needles, handling trash and dirty linen and transferring blood or body fluids from a syringe to a specimen container and missing the target) [13].

Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess the awareness of HCWs regarding needle stick injuries and the practices of precautionary measures by them in public and private hospitals of Hyderabad city and to compare this awareness and practices between the

HCWs of private and government hospital to have a better picture of the healthcare system.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This present study was a cross sectional survey conducted in two public and two private sector tertiary care hospitals of Hyderabad during the months of July to September 2018.

Non-probability purposive sampling technique used for selection of sample from different medical, surgical, gynecological wards, Intensive care units (ICU) and Laboratory. Self-administered written questionnaire prepared specifically for the current study used to collect data from Nursing staff & Laboratory Technician of public and private hospital of Hyderabad. Questionnaire comprises of three parts. First part contains questions related to socio-demographic features, second part consists of questions related to participant's knowledge of needle stick Injuries like disease spread from it, precautionary measures etc. and last part consist of their routine practices and precautionary measures they take for protecting themselves from NSIs. One point given to each correct question and total number of correct replies were calculated.

Informed oral consent taken from each participant after explaining study purpose. All study participants

and hospital administration also assured about the confidentiality and anonymity of the information. Before filling out the questionnaire, the respondents explained in detail about NSI i.e. any injury that occurs due to needles in hospital setting for infusions or drawing of blood. Interviews offered in either local or English language according to the convenience of the participants. Awareness level of HCWs was measured after calculating total correct replies of each participant. Those who replied less than 15 questions considered as low awareness, 15-19 correct considered as average awareness and 20 or more correct labeled as highly aware.

The collected data entered in the SPSS version 21. Descriptive analysis presented in tabulated and figure form. While Chi square test used to assess the difference in the awareness level. Significance level was set at p-value ≤ 0.05 .

RESULTS:

A total 280 healthcare workers (HCWs) invited to participate in the present study of which 250 given consent for participation. Out of 250 participants, 30 (12%) never heard about needle stick injuries (NSIs) so they were also excluded from study. The final study population comprise of 200 HCWs from public and private hospitals of Hyderabad.

We asked all participants about their socio-demographic features. Majority of the participants belongs to private sector hospital comparison with the public hospital. The mean age of HCWs was 32.5±

9.02 years. Most of them belong to age group 38 to 47 years. Among the participants, majority of them were male. Most of the HCWs were nursing staff followed by Midwives and technicians. (Table1)

Table1: Socio-demographic features of participants (n=200)

		Public n(%)	Private n(%)	Total n(%)
		94(47)	106(53)	200
Age group	18-27	22(23.4)	20(19)	42(21)
	28-37	32(34)	40(37.7)	72(36)
	38-47	40(42.6)	46(43.3)	86(43)
Sex	Male	60(64)	46(43.4)	106(53)
	Female	34(36)	60(56.6)	94(47)
Designation	Nursing Staff	46(49)	59(55.7)	105(52.5)
	Midwives	22(23.4)	22(20.7)	44(22)
	Technicians	26(27.6)	25(23.6)	51(25.5)

Experience	0 to 5 years	47(50)	57(53.7)	104(52)
	6 to 10 years	24(25.5)	25(23.7)	49(24.5)
	11 to 15 years	23(24.5)	24(22.6)	47(23.5)
Ward Posting	Gynae/Obstetrics	20(21.3)	38(36)	58(29)
	Surgery	17(18.1)	15(14)	32(16)
	Medicine	16(17)	18(17)	34(17)
	Emergency	21(22.3)	19(18)	40(20)
	Operation Theatre	20(21.3)	16(15)	36(18)

Figure 1 below representing the prevalence of NSI among HCWs in public and private sector hospitals. Large majority of the HCWs suffered from NSIs during their career in public sector facility comparison with the private sector staff. Majority of them were nursing staff that suffered more than any other HCWs. Half of the midwives and two third of technicians also suffered from the NSIs during their career (Figure 1).

Figure1: Distribution of participants according the NSIs during their career (n=200)

Table 2 below is demonstrating the distribution of replies of the participants from public and private hospitals. Participants when inquired about the needle stick injuries (NSI) to assess their knowledge, majority of them correctly replied to the question that NSI includes “injuries from infected syringes and sharps”. Similarly, majority most of them replied correctly that Hepatitis B, C and HIV are the common diseases spread by NSIs. In reply to the question about the precautionary measures of NSIs, replies were almost even distributed i.e. almost half of them correctly replied the precautionary measures for NSIs (proper discard and disposal of used syringes in appropriate place) (Table 2).

Table2: Awareness related questions from participants (n=200)

QUESTIONS	REPLIES	Public n (%)	Private n (%)	Total n (%)
		94(47)	106(53)	200
Needle Stick Injuries (NSIs) include	- Correct	39(41.5)	67(63)	106(53)
	- Incorrect	55(58.5)	39(37)	94(47)
Diseases spread by NSIs	- Correct	51(54.3)	82(77.3)	133(66.5)
	- Incorrect	43(45.7)	24(22.7)	67(33.5)
Precautionary measures of NSIs	- Correct	45(48)	61(57.5)	106(53)
	- Incorrect	49(52)	45(42.5)	94(47)

Participants from public and private hospitals were asked for their opinion about “which is the most frequent cause of NSI”? Majority of HCWs from public hospitals believe that recapping of used syringes after using them is the most frequent cause of NSIs occurin comparison with private hospital participants where majority thinks that during medication NSIs occur most frequently While the overall most common cause was recapping of syringes as use reported by most of the participants. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Replies of participants (public and private hospital) about the frequent causes of NSIs (n=200)

Figure3 below is showing the proportional distribution of participant’s reply to question about their awareness of any preventive guideline of NSIs. In reply, of the question majority of participants reported that they have not heard about the NSIs preventive and precautionary guidelines at all. (Figure3)

Figure 3: Proportional distribution of participant's awareness of any NSI preventive guidelines n=200

Questions related to the routine practices regarding handling of sharps and syringes also asked from the participants. Majority of them replied that they never use instruments tray or syringe tray regularly to keep syringes on it. While more than, half of them replied that they use sharp disposal containers. Half of them also replied that they discard needles properly in containers after using it. Most of them responded positively that they always enquire their patient's history prior to injecting them. Surprisingly, majority of them do not use needle cutters for disposing used needles nor they use gloves when deal with needle. (Table 3)

Table3: Distribution of replies of questions related to routine practice of participants (n=200)

PRACTICE QUESTIONS		Hospital Setting		
		Public	Private	Total
		n(%)	n(%)	n(%)
		94(47)	106(53)	200
Do you regularly use tray to keep syringes?	Yes	41(43.6)	52(49)	93(46.5)
	No	53(56.4)	54(51)	107(53.5)
Do you regularly use sharp disposal containers?	Yes	48(51)	61(57.5)	109(54.5)
	No	46(49)	45(42.5)	91(45.5)
Do you discard needles properly in container after use?	Yes	48(51)	55(52)	103(51.5)
	No	46(49)	51(48)	97(48.5)
Do you enquire patients about their disease history prior injecting them?	Yes, always	45(48)	52(49)	97(48.5)
	Yes, sometimes	30(32)	30(28)	60(30)
	No	19(20)	24(23)	43(21.5)
Do you use needle cutter for disposing used needles?	Yes	30(32)	54(51)	84(42)
	No	64(68)	52(49)	116(58)
How often you use gloves when deal with needle	Always	11(11.7)	31(29)	42(21)
	Most of times	14(15)	16(15)	30(15)
	Rarely	18(19)	43(40)	61(30)
	Never	51(54.3)	17(16)	68(34)

Participants from both public and private hospitals were asked if they have ever attended any bio-safety course. Surprisingly, majority of them never attended such course until date. (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Proportional distribution of participants reply about Bio-safety course (n=200)

There was statistically significant difference (p value < 0.05) of awareness found between health care workers in public and private sector hospital. HCWs of private sector hospital were more aware about the NSIs and its preventive/precautionary measures.

Table 4: Difference of awareness level of HCWs in public and private hospitals (n=200)

AWARENESS LEVEL	HOSPITAL SETTING		P-value
	Public (94)	Private (106)	
<15 (low)	39	18	<0.05*
15-19 (average)	43	51	
20 and above (high)	22	27	

* P -value =0.13

DISCUSSION:

Needle stick injuries remain a potential source of infection among the health care workers (HCWs) and major cause of transmission of blood borne life-threatening infections [7]. It is most frequently occurring occupational injury in the health care settings in public and private sector [10]. NSIs are one occupational injuries that are responsible for the transmission of lethal viruses resulting in diseases like Hepatitis B & C and AIDS [15]. Large number of strategies are available for evading the burden of diseases linked with the NSIs. These strategies include awareness, vaccination against Hepatitis B, reduction in the number of injections, use of safer devices, post-exposure prophylaxis etc [15].

In Pakistan, it is a major occupational health problem between medical and dental HCWs [14]. Ministry of health and medical community has ignored importance of occupational health and safety as well as disaster management during teaching and training programs [14]. Overcrowding of hospitals, limited number of HCWs and unhygienic practices makes the condition worse in country like Pakistan. Lack of

awareness and proportionate training of human resource as well as inexperience is also another serious factor that causes rise in toll of such occupational injuries and ultimately burden of diseases in our country.

Several studies demonstrated the level of awareness of HCWs but still little known about the fact that awareness or lack of knowledge about the possible risk factors of NSIs can have any impact on the attitudes and behaviors or not. Nursing staff showed the low levels of awareness. Majority of them belongs to public sector hospital. Despite the fact that nursing staff very frequently been exposed to the patients and encountered NSIs still having no negative behavior towards recapping of syringes. At the same time, they also ignore to wear the protective clothing and gloves while performing procedures on their patients. On the other hand, most of the nursing staff also reported NSIs.

Majority of participants of our study were aware of term NSIs but amongst the HCWs from public sector hospital do not know about the NSIs properly.

Approximately 66% of HCWs in this study were aware that Hepatitis B transmitted through blood. Much higher findings of awareness about the Hepatitis B transmission reported by Suliman et al. from Sudan (2016) [16].

This study assessed the knowledge of HCWs related to the diseases transmitted and precautionary measures for preventing different injuries. Almost two third of HCWs who participated were aware of the fact hepatitis B, C and HIV can be transmitted by NSIs while one third of them do not know about the diseases that transmitted by NSIs.

In the present study, prevalence of NSIs in the public hospital was 44% compared to 26.4% in the private one. This difference could be due to the high patient turnover in public settings as opposed to private settings. The highest proportion of injuries in both hospitals occurred while disposing of or recapping needles (42.4% and 62.7% in public and private hospital, respectively), followed by during manipulation in-patient (34.1% and 25.5% in public and private hospital, respectively).

Furthermore, highest rate (47%) of NSIs was observed among the HCWs of age group 18 to 27 years in our study. These findings are consistent with the studies conducted by Hosoglu et al. (2009) [17] and Muralidhar et al. 2010 [18]. These differences in incidence of NSIs reflects the possible limited professional experience as well as these young professionals tends to be more enthusiastic and aggressive in their but they ignore the universal professional guidelines or they don't even aware of these guidelines. Our study also demonstrated that among HCWs, female staff predominated in NSIs. Similar difference between genders in NSIs reported by Singu et al. 2008 in India [19].

This predominance of female gender may be due to the reason that majority of HCWs in the hospital are female gender. More than two third (77%) of HCWs reported that they have suffered from NSIs during their career in the present study. Majority (91%) of them were nursing staff from public as well as private sector reported that they suffered from NSIs once or twice in their career. This may be due to the nature of job of nursing staff as they more frequently deals with the syringes and sharp instruments. One study conducted in Sudan by Suliman et al. in 2016 [16] demonstrated that majority (40%) of nursing staff in their study suffered from NSI. Najma et al. 2013 [20] from Karachi also reported that 77% of their HCWs suffered from NSIs once or twice in their career.

Another study conducted at Alexandria Hospital by Hanafi et al. 2011 [21] reported that 68% of the HCWs in their study had sustained at least one NSI in past one year duration. A study by Sharma et al from India in 2010 [22] reported a bit high prevalence (79.5%) of HCWs in their study suffered from one or more NSIs in their career these findings are consistent with the findings of our study.

Lack of access to personal protective equipment like gloves, gowns, masks etc. as well as hand hygiene maintenance practices are non-specific protective methods against many infectious diseases.

Marked negligence in this area not only increases the toll of NSIs related morbidities but also increase the risk of spread of such lethal diseases. Wearing gloves is to be one of the most important precautionary method against NSIs but several of the HCWs had not been wearing them at the time of their injury, higher proportions among the nurses and the technicians. It is noteworthy that 34% of all HCWs never used to wear gloves when handling the syringes or needles. About 30% of them rarely use gloves during their duty while handling patients. Higher proportion of HCWs was nursing staff that belongs to public sector hospital. It may be due to non-availability of hand gloves for nursing staff, technicians or midwives and improper attitude and behavior towards preventive measures of NSI. Importance of occupational health and safety as well as disaster management in teaching and training is always been ignored systematically by the medical fraternity.

Number of needle and needle less devices with safety features are now available. These devices have decreased the incidence of NSIs by 62-88%. In the current study, less than half of the participants knew about the safety devices and use of the preventive measures was inadequate. Even in practice majority (58%) of them never used needle cutter in their routine practice. Our study revealed that information of about 61% of injuries were not registered or reported into an official record. Similar findings that are closer to our study also reported by Cui et al. (66%) in 2018 [23] and Jahangiri et al. (60.2%) in 2016 [24]. Our study findings proportion is higher than reported by Makary et al. (51%) in 2007 [25]. Foremost reason for failure to report such injury is non-serious and unprofessional attitudes of higher ups towards such reporting. Non-availability of appropriate guidelines in tertiary care hospitals especially in the public sector hospitals of the city. Furthermore, lack of time and overcrowded hospitals as well as perception of low risk of infection by the HCWs enforce them to ignore to report such

injuries. Along with strengths this study also have limitations, one of the potential problem in the study is selection bias. However, representation of both public and private sector hospitals but still all shift staff did not participated in the study. Inclusion of more private and public hospitals of the city would reduce any selection bias. Furthermore, restricted time and budget is another limitation in our study.

CONCLUSION:

NSIs were observed in all categories of HCWs. Prevalence of NSIs was high among the HCWs especially among the public sector HCWs. Majority of nursing staff suffered from NSIs. Level of awareness in our study was found to be very low among the HCWs of Public sector hospital. Highest proportion of nursing staff was not aware of basic precautionary measures of NSIs.

Recommendations:

Hospitals and nursing institutes must organize and arrange preparatory courses about the prevention methods of NSIs and other occupation related injuries. Elimination of practices like recapping of used syringes need to discouraged by the health facilities. Availability of proper and safe disposal of needles, syringes and sharps must be ensured by the health facilities.

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